

It's about her: male within-season movements are related to mate searching in a songbird

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ABSTRACT

In species with resource-defense mating systems (such as most temperate-breeding songbirds), male dispersal is often considered to be limited in both frequency and spatial extent. When dispersal occurs within a breeding season, the favored explanation is ecological resource tracking. In contrast, movements of male birds associated with temporary emigration, such as polyterritoriality (i.e., defense of an additional location after attracting a female in the initial territory), are usually attributed to mate searching. We suggest that male dispersal and polyterritoriality are functionally related, and that mate searching may be a unifying hypothesis for predicting the within-season movements of male songbirds. Here, we test three key predictions derived from this hypothesis in Wood Warblers *Phylloscopus sibilatrix*. We collected data on the spatial behavior of 107 males between 2017 and 2019, and related male movements to a new territory (both in a dispersal and polyterritorial context) to mating potential in the current territory. Most males dispersed from their territories within days or weeks after failing to attract a female, despite occupying territories in apparently suitable habitat. Probability of polyterritoriality by paired males increased after the peak fertile period of their mate. Males never dispersed following nest predation if the female remained to renest. Thus, our data are consistent with the hypothesis that both movement types are functionally related to mate searching.

INTRODUCTION

In his seminal paper describing sex-biased dispersal in birds and mammals, Greenwood (1980) suggested that species with mating systems based on male resource defense (*sensu* Emlen & Oring, 1977) should exhibit limited male dispersal (defined as permanent emigration from a territory) and, consequently, often be monogamous. The argument is based on a presumed advantage of familiarity for territory establishment. According to Greenwood, the cost imposed by unfamiliarity would frequently prevent males from moving to a new territory, even if their present territory is poor and better ones are available. By extension, because territory establishment is considered a prerequisite for mating, movement to track changing or ephemeral spatiotemporal patterns in mate availability (i.e., mate searching) would be futile.

Dispersal theory rarely assumes differential ability to acquire a resource based on familiarity (Li and Kokko 2019), and numerous theoretical studies highlight how dispersal can be an adaptive response to suboptimal local conditions (Bowler and Benton 2005; Clobert et al. 2009). Empirical studies have also reported that even within a breeding season, male movement to new territories can occur frequently in territorial bird species (Dale et al. 2005; Williams and Boyle 2018; Cooper and Marra 2020; Newton 2000). Most studies of within-season movements in territorial birds relate movement decisions to poor or deteriorating habitat, without assessing mate availability (Betts et al. 2008; Gilroy et al. 2010; Frey et al. 2016; Williams and Boyle 2018; Williams and Boyle 2019; Ceresa et al. 2020). Theoretical studies demonstrating the importance of mate availability for dispersal and settlement decisions (e.g., Gilroy and Lockwood 2012, 2016) also uphold the assumption that in territorial species, it is females that typically assess and respond to mate availability (with male decisions based on territory

availability alone). Thus, while male dispersal in territorial species may occur more frequently than Greenwood once suggested, mate searching remains largely absent as an explanation.

In contrast to dispersal, temporary emigration by males in the form of extra-territorial forays or polyterritoriality (defined as defense of an additional location after attracting a female in the initial territory) has long been assumed to be related to mate searching. Male foray movements to pursue extra-pair copulations have been recorded in at least 39 species (Westneat and Stewart 2003). Polyterritoriality is also taxonomically widespread in temperate-breeding birds (Møller 1986; Korpimäki 1988; Ford 1996), and distances between the initial nest and “secondary territories” can be substantial (>1 km, Rätti et al. 1994 and references therein). Male polyterritorial and foray movements often coincide with the onset of laying or incubation by the female (Alatalo and Lundberg 1984; Evans et al. 2008), which in many species is associated with a decline in female copulatory activity (Arvidsson 1992; Westneat 1993; Sheldon and Burke 1994). Thus, polyterritorial and foray behaviors fit theoretical expectations that males should shift from mate-guarding to mate-searching once the “fertilization window” of their current partner has passed (Harts and Kokko 2013). Such movements further demonstrate that, in contrast to Greenwood’s assumption, resource defense and mobile mate searching are not inherently incompatible.

Individuals move for different reasons at different times, and thus there are multiple ultimate explanations for the within-season movements of territorial male birds (Smith et al. 2020). Nevertheless, as outlined above, distinct movement patterns (e.g., temporary vs. permanent emigration) are often assigned distinct functions (e.g., dispersal is for resource tracking, polyterritoriality and extra-territorial forays are for reproductive enhancement). While

such distinctions may sometimes be valid, they may also obscure the presence of common proximate cues and ultimate causes across different “movement types” (Shaw 2020). We propose that mate searching may be a unifying conceptual framework for understanding the movements of male birds within the breeding season (Fig. 1). According to this framework, a male’s decision to temporarily or permanently move from one territory to another is a response to a cue that the potential for mating in the current territory is low (or lower than it would be elsewhere). Thus, we suggest that many if not most within-season movements of male birds to new territories (or intrusions onto the territories of others) can be attributed to gaining or maintaining access to females.

Here, we evaluate whether this mate searching framework can be applied to explain the within-season movements of male Wood Warblers (*Phylloscopus sibilatrix*), a songbird species that can be polyterritorial (Temrin 1984; Temrin et al. 1984) and has been reported to make long-distance dispersal movements within a breeding season (Herremans 1993; Norman 1994; Riedinger 1995). We investigated relationships between male movement decisions, ecological conditions and current mating potential in the initial territory to test the following three predictions emerging from the mate searching hypothesis: 1) the majority of unpaired males will disperse from (i.e., abandon) their territories prior to the end of the breeding season despite occupying territories in apparently suitable habitat; 2) polyterritorial movement of paired males will coincide with a decline in perceived mating potential in their current territory (i.e., decline in receptivity of the female to copulations); 3) dispersal of males following nest predation (i.e., from a territory in apparently unsuitable habitat) will depend on whether the female remains to

renest or not. We then discuss the potential generality of mate searching as an explanatory framework for the within-season movements of male birds.

METHODS

Study Species and Study Area

We studied Wood Warblers breeding in the Jura Mountains of northwestern Switzerland. The landscape in this region is composed of steep hills and narrow valleys covered by a mosaic of mixed-deciduous forest and pastureland. Between 2017 and 2019 we worked in seven study sites (i.e., forests). Study sites ranged in elevation from roughly 450 m to ca. 1000 m above sea level, and from approximately 50 ha to 180 ha in size. The total area encompassed by the study sites was ca. 760 ha.

Wood Warblers are small (~9 g) long-distance migratory songbirds that breed in forests across the western Palearctic. This species has been characterized as “nomadic,” exhibiting large interannual fluctuations in local abundance that are negatively correlated with fluctuations in rodent abundance (Wesołowski et al. 2009; Grendelmeier et al. 2019). Males begin arriving on the breeding grounds in mid-April, followed shortly by females. Females choose the nest site, which is always on the ground, and build the nest with the male usually in close attendance (Cramp 1992). Females will reneest after failed nest attempts (up until late June in our study population), but reneesting after the initial nest has fledged is apparently quite rare (Cramp 1992). After nest-building is completed, males are often only sporadically present at the nest until the eggs hatch, when they usually assist with feeding the nestlings.

Terminology and Definitions

We considered a “territory” to be an area in which males sang and that they defended against other males. In order to avoid including individuals who may have been passing through, we restricted our analysis to males who were observed singing within our study areas for at least 5 days (Lawn 1982), albeit not necessarily in the same territory. We classified any shift of ≥ 150 m between territory centroids (see section 2.4.2 for how territory centroids were spatially defined) as a “within-season movement.” We chose the 150 m distance threshold based on previous studies of polyterritoriality in Wood Warblers (Temrin 1984; Temrin et al. 1984), as well as our own observation of the relatively small (~ 50 m diameter) areas in which singing activity occurred. It is also similar to the 100 m threshold used in some studies of breeding dispersal in other passerine birds (Dale et al. 2005; Williams and Boyle 2018). Following (Dale et al. 2005), we defined “dispersal” as permanent emigration from one territory to another territory located ≥ 150 m away by either an unpaired male or by a male (or female) after a failed nesting attempt. We defined “polyterritoriality” as temporary emigration from the current nesting territory (or “primary” territory) to an additional “secondary” territory ≥ 150 m away. In the context of polyterritoriality, “temporary” emigration refers to the fact that paired males repeatedly return to their primary territory (i.e., they do not permanently shift to a new territory). Wood Warbler males advertise and defend secondary territories in bouts ranging from minutes to hours (particularly in the morning), between which they return to the primary territory with the nesting female (Temrin et al. 1984, Temrin and Stenius 1994).

Data Collection

Capturing and recording male spatial behavior:

We surveyed our study sites for Wood Warblers from mid-April until early July of each year. During surveys, we walked a set route covering the entire study site, marking the locations of all singing birds (ringed and unringed) as well as behaviors indicative of nesting. To increase our chances of detecting silent individuals, we played a one-minute recording of a Wood Warbler in full song (i.e., “long trills” and “piping songs,” Cramp 1992) every ca. 200 m. Surveys took place during morning hours, though they often extended into the early afternoon at larger sites. Although surveys were conducted ca. every two weeks in 2017, and ca. once per week in 2018/19 (see below for methodological changes following 2017), study sites (or at least portions thereof) were visited every 4 days on average (range 1 – 16 days) for additional tasks such as capturing or nest checks.

Most males were captured using mist nets (Ecotone, Gdynia, PL) and playback of conspecific song (n=127). A few males were captured while provisioning nestlings (n=6). Females were captured with a dipnet on the nest during incubation (n=54) or with a mist net while feeding nestlings (n=8). Females readily returned to the nest after capture, except for two individuals caught during incubation that apparently abandoned the nest. All individuals were marked with 3 plastic color rings (2.1 – 2.3 mm) and a numbered aluminum ring. In 2017 and 2018, most males (93%, n=42 and 56%, n=50, respectively) also received a small (0.3 g) radio transmitter (Holohil, Carp, ON, CAN), which was mounted on the bird using a leg-loop harness (Rappole and Tipton 1991). There were no apparent ill effects of the transmitter on the birds, as they generally resumed normal activity within minutes of release and flew about unhindered.

In 2017, when almost all captured males were fitted with a radio transmitter, we did 2-hour telemetry sessions with a given individual. We used a Yagi antenna to locate individuals initially, but then relied on visual and audio cues once we were in the vicinity of the focal bird. We marked location points every three minutes. For each individual, whenever possible we conducted telemetry sessions in both the morning and afternoon hours. For each location point, we noted if the bird was singing (i.e., “acting territorial”) or not.

During the 2017 field season, we observed two key patterns of spatial behavior that led us to adjust our data collection strategy in the following two field seasons. First, within a given telemetry session, males generally remained within the same singing area. Between days, however, singing locations could shift substantially (> 1 km). Secondly, turnover rate within the study areas was high throughout the breeding season, with the locations and identities of birds present in an area shifting regularly. We therefore adjusted our sampling methods for collecting location data on color-ringed birds (with and without transmitters) in 2018 and 2019 by reducing the amount of time we spent with a given individual from two hours to 15 minutes. This approach yielded five location points per individual per session (one point every 3 minutes), which still allowed us to delineate a daily “territory” while also covering more of the study area on a given visit. Spending less time per individual but surveying a larger area more frequently increased our ability to detect territory shifts, departures and arrivals of new individuals in the study area.

In all of the following analyses, we used locations recorded visually and using radio telemetry where males were observed singing either the full song or the “short song,” the latter of which males sing when in close proximity to a female (Cramp 1992). The observations were

done during telemetry sessions and when resighting the males at any point during fieldwork. In addition to noting male singing locations, intensive nest searching in the study areas enabled us to locate the vast majority of nests present (see the following section for details of nest searching and monitoring).

Telemetry efforts were focused within the bounds of our study areas, and we made few attempts to locate individuals outside of them. Thus, given the similar spatial extent of sampling as well as the presence of vocal cues and frequent visual contact with radio-tracked individuals, detection of long-distance movements was not biased toward individuals with transmitters. We confirmed this by comparing the step lengths representing movements (i.e., ≥ 150 m) made by birds with and without transmitters (see Supporting Information S1).

All field data collection protocols were approved by cantonal and federal authorities. Capturing and ringing were done with permits from the Federal Office of Environment (FOEN), Switzerland, and attaching transmitters with permits from the respective cantonal veterinary offices (permit numbers BL468/25097 and BL468/28642).

Nest searching and monitoring

We located Wood Warbler nests through behavioral observations of pairs and/or females. Upon finding a nest, we marked its location and checked it every three to five days. We also monitored the majority (85%, $n=94$) of nests with cameras (Reconyx, Holmen, WI, USA), which we set up during the egg-laying stage at the earliest. The cameras enabled us to observe nest attendance by the adults when we were not present, and to know precisely when nest failure

occurred. Given the frequency of our visits to the study sites, the extensive time spent following and observing individual birds, and obvious changes in male singing behavior associated with pairing (Cramp 1992), we are confident that we found most of the females/nests within our study areas.

Data Analysis

General Information

All data processing and statistical analyses were conducted in R (R Core Team, 2020). Data sets and R codes are available at the Zenodo Open Repository and Archive (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8382146>; Luepold et al. 2023). Logistic regression models were fit by Hamiltonian Monte Carlo simulations in Stan via the *brms* package (Bürkner 2017) using 4 Markov chains and 10,000 iterations. We used the default prior settings in *brms*, consisting of flat priors (so-called “improper distributions”) for the model coefficients (fixed effects), a half-student t (3, 0, 10) distribution for the variance parameters and a student t (3, 0, 2.5) distribution for random effects intercepts (Bürkner 2017; Lewandowski et al. 2009). Model convergence was assessed by visual inspection of trace plots as well as examination of \hat{R} values (all < 1.005) and effective sample size. We used the 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of the posterior distributions of model parameters and model predictions as lower and upper limits of the 95% credible intervals (CrI).

Processing location data of marked birds for analysis

From all observations, we constructed a location history containing a single point location per day for each male by averaging all the coordinates for a given male on each day he was observed (hereafter “daily location”). All nests where a male was known to be the social father were included as (inferred) daily location points for him on the day the nest was initiated. When nests were not found during the building stage and dates had to be back-calculated based on subsequent events (e.g., hatching), the following timings were used: 14 days for incubation, initiated on the day the clutch was completed (Cramp 1992); nest initiation was seven days prior to clutch initiation (S. Luepold, pers. obs.). We determined a male’s status on a given date based on behavioral observations in the field, which was not always possible to do unambiguously. Males that defended territories but apparently did not have nests in the study area were assumed to be unpaired, though it is possible that some may have had nests located outside the study sites.

From these daily locations we then derived territory centroids by calculating the distances between all daily locations for each male and averaging locations within 150 m of each other to obtain a single point (centroid) per territory. For males with nests, the nest was considered the territory centroid for all observations within 150 m of it.

Frequency of dispersal by unpaired males in relation to habitat

To test prediction 1, we employed a multi-pronged approach. First, we used the following criterion to determine whether a given male dispersed or not while unpaired: for a male with no known active nest in the study sites, we considered him to have dispersed if he permanently

emigrated from a territory where he failed to find a mate prior to the end of June. Males leaving up to this point could have potentially still attracted a female in a new territory, as the latest date of clutch initiation we observed in our population was June 29th. In some cases (n=41 movements by 34 males), males dispersed to another location within the study sites and we calculated the distance between territory centroids (see Results). In other cases, dispersal was inferred based on disappearance (n=52 males). While it is possible that some disappearances were due to mortality, the number of individuals that disappeared suggests that the vast majority of cases were due to emigration out of the study sites. Based on observations of 85 males while they were unpaired (equivalent to 388 daily locations), we determined that 70% of males dispersed from a territory at least once while unpaired.

After establishing the prevalence of dispersal in unpaired males, we then assessed whether emigration occurred even when territories were in suitable habitat, as predicted by the mate searching hypothesis. We addressed this question from two different angles: (1) by comparing habitat features in territories occupied by paired and unpaired males (assuming that if territories abandoned by unpaired males were in suitable habitat, ecological conditions should be equivalent to those in territories occupied by paired males; (2) by comparing habitat features in successive territories of the same males (assuming that if territories abandoned by unpaired males were in suitable habitat, ecological conditions should be equivalent to those in the territories to which these males dispersed).

For the above two analyses, we considered two categories of habitat features: proxy of predation risk (rodent activity index, *RAI*) and vegetation structure (“light detection and ranging”, a.k.a., LiDAR variables). Detailed descriptions of each metric and how it was derived

can be found in the Supporting Information (S2), but we briefly report a few salient points here. The rodent activity index was calculated from track plates (Connors et al. 2005; Grendelmeier et al. 2017) distributed in a subset of the study sites in 2017 (two sites) and 2018 (three sites). Previous studies at various spatial scales have reported that Wood Warblers avoid breeding in areas where rodents are abundant (Grendelmeier et al. 2019; Pasinelli et al. 2016). For the vegetation structure variables, we used three LiDAR-derived metrics that were previously found to predict breeding habitat selection and occupancy in Wood Warblers in our study region (Huber et al. 2016; Huber et al. 2017): mean vegetation height (*meanVH*), standard deviation of canopy height > 3m (*sdCH3*) and penetration rate 5 to 1 m above ground (*pen5_1*). *MeanVH* indicates overall stand height, *sdCH3* is a measure of heterogeneity in canopy height, and *pen5_1* provides a measure of the density of the shrub/regeneration layer.

For each of the habitat metrics, values were calculated within a 25 m radius of territory centroids. For *RAI*, *meanVH* and *sdCH3*, which were all in raster format, pixel values within the 25 m radius territory circle were averaged (pixel size was 10x10 m for *RAI*, 2x2 m for *meanVH* and 1x1 m for *sdCH3*). The variable *pen5_1* was calculated as the ratio of LiDAR signals below 1 m to signals below 5 m.

To compare habitat in the territories of unpaired males to habitat in the territories of paired males, we calculated these same four habitat metrics within a 25 m radius of nests (representing the territory centroid for paired males). We then used two methods to assess whether there was evidence that unpaired males occupied territories in unsuitable habitat, and hence, that habitat rather than lack of a mate was driving their dispersal decisions. First, for each habitat metric, we compared the data distribution for paired and unpaired territories using box

and whisker plots. If the two distributions overlapped substantially (e.g., if one interquartile interval was contained within the other), we considered this as evidence that the two territory types did not differ. Second, we used a logistic regression model to relate “territory type” (“0” for unpaired male, “1” for paired male) to habitat features within the territory. Because we did not have track plate data for all the territories for which we had LiDAR data, we ran separate models to examine the effect of the rodent activity index and the effects of vegetation structure variables. For males that had multiple territories (n=15 in the rodent activity model, n=44 in the vegetation structure model), we selected one at random to include in the analysis. We present standardized estimated effects with 95% credible intervals for each habitat metric. When a given credible interval included 0 and only small to very small effect sizes ($-1.25 \leq \beta \leq 1.25$, Chen et al. 2010), we considered the habitat metric unimportant as a predictor of whether a territory was occupied by paired or unpaired male.

To determine whether there was evidence that successive territories occupied by the same male differed in habitat, we followed the same procedure as described above for paired and unpaired male territories: box and whisker plots to visualize data distribution, and logistic regression to examine whether habitat metrics could predict whether a territory was the first and second territory occupied by a given male.

Probability of polyterritorial movement in relation to mating potential in the current territory

To test prediction 2, we examined if movement to a secondary territory occurred, and if so, during a period when mating potential in the primary territory was high or low. Centroids of

secondary territories were calculated as described above (see section 2.4.2) from 326 daily locations of 62 males during the period from when their mate arrived until eggs hatched (i.e., prior to the onset of paternal care). Mating potential in the primary territory was defined as follows: “high” corresponded to the peak fertilization window (i.e., the nest-building period), “low” corresponded to the period outside the peak fertilization window (i.e., egg-laying and incubation). Although females are physiologically still fertile during the egg-laying period, studies of the copulation behavior of multiple passerines (including *Phylloscopus* species) have shown that copulation activity peaks before the first egg is laid, and that female solicitation of copulations declines markedly during egg-laying (Westneat 1993; Arvidsson 1992; Sheldon and Burke 1994). Thus, the potential for a male to achieve further paternity gains through mating with a female after she has initiated a clutch is often significantly reduced.

We used logistic regression to relate the binary response variable *Movement* to the categorical predictor representing mating potential (*Mate*) in the primary territory. Individuals that were never observed in a secondary territory during a given period were assigned a *Movement* value of zero for that period, while individuals that were observed in secondary territories were assigned a *Movement* value of one for the period in which the movement occurred. For 29 males, we only had data during one of the two periods (high only: n=8; low only: n=21). In the model, we included male ID as a random effect, as well as a covariate representing the mean number of conspecifics (unpaired males and breeding pairs) observed within a 150 m radius of the primary territory (i.e., nest) to account for potential effects of local density (*Local Density*) on movement decisions.

Probability of dispersal following nest predation in relation to mating potential in the current territory

To test prediction 3, we analyzed the spatial behavior of males following a nest predation event. The analytical approach was the same as described above for polyterritorial movements, and we used a Bernoulli model to relate male movement to mating potential in the current territory (*Mate*). In this analysis, we categorized males as having moved if we observed them singing in a new territory ≥ 150 m from their previous nest or if they disappeared within a week of the predation event. If they remained within 150 m of the predated nest for at least a week, they were considered to have stayed. We defined mating potential as “high” if the female stayed to renest within 150 m of the predated nest, and “zero” if the female disappeared (due to dispersal or death). Of 23 females that disappeared, three were confirmed to have been predated (determined via camera and/or physical evidence), four were known to have dispersed (based on known renest locations), and 16 were presumed to have dispersed (no evidence of predation but never seen again).

For males who had multiple failed nesting attempts, we included only their first attempt in the analysis. We included two cases of predator-induced clutch abandonment (as determined from camera footage) as “nest predation” events in this analysis since they also presumably resulted in elevated perceived predation risk. Due to the decline in singing activity in July, we excluded all nest failures that occurred after June because these males most likely did not move to defend a new territory.

RESULTS

Frequency of dispersal by unpaired males in relation to habitat

The majority of males (70%) for whom we had spatial behavior data when they were unpaired (n=81) abandoned one or more territories in apparently good habitat prior to the end of the breeding season (i.e., prior to the latest observed clutch initiation date of June 29), thereby supporting prediction 1. The mean tenure at a territory location where a male failed to attract a mate was 9 days (n=93, range: 1 – 41 days). We documented a total of 93 dispersal movements by 61 unpaired males: 52 movements were assumed based on disappearances, 41 were of known distance (representing movements by 34 individuals). The mean distance between territories was 703 m (n=41, range: 150 – 4156 m).

Territories occupied by paired and unpaired males, as well as successive territories occupied by the same individual, overlapped substantially for each habitat metric (Figs. 2 and 3). In addition, there was little evidence that habitat characteristics could predict whether a territory was occupied by a paired or unpaired male, or whether a territory was a male's first or his second (95% credible intervals included 0 and values close to it) (Table 1).

Probability of male polyterritorial movement in relation to mating potential in the current territory

Out of 62 males that we monitored during the period between when they attracted a mate and eggs hatched, 14 were confirmed as polyterritorial (i.e., we observed them on a secondary territory). The true frequency of polyterritoriality was likely higher than we observed because we

could not track each individual every day. Three individuals were observed on multiple secondary territories, such that the total number of polyterritorial movements was 18. The mean distance between primary and secondary territories was 380 m (range: 150 – 981 m, n=18). There was a strong relationship between male movement probability and mating potential in the current (primary) territory, with males being much more likely to move when mating potential was low (Table 2, Fig. 4A). We only observed one individual move to a secondary territory while the mating potential in the current territory was still high (i.e., prior to the onset of laying by the female).

Probability of male dispersal after nest predation in relation to mating potential in the current territory

We recorded male movement responses to 29 nest predation events. Males invariably remained when the female stayed to renest (n=6), when mating potential in the current territory was high. Because none of the males with a female that stayed emigrated, mating potential in the current territory had an estimated effect of large magnitude (Table 3). Note that this estimate is strongly influenced by the prior distribution because the value of the response was always zero for one group (i.e., when *Mate* = “high”), and therefore the mean movement probability of this group was zero (for which the log-odds is not defined). When the female dispersed or died (n=23), males had a high probability of emigrating (0.87, CrI=0.68 – 0.97, Fig. 4B). Out of 19 male dispersal events following nest predation, 14 were disappearances and five were movements of known distance (mean: 403 m, range: 178 – 711 m).

DISCUSSION

In his classic paper on sex-biased dispersal in birds and mammals, Greenwood (1980) attributed differences between these taxa to differences in the importance of mobile mate searching as a means for males to increase their fitness. Due to the resource-defense mating system prevalent among birds, male mate searching was assumed to be of limited relevance. Here, we propose that mate searching may represent a unifying conceptual framework for understanding within-season movements of male birds, and we evaluated this hypothesis by testing three predictions related to permanent and temporary emigration decisions in Wood Warblers. All three predictions were supported by our data.

In support of our first prediction, we found that most males (70%) dispersed from a territory at least once while unpaired, even when the territory was in apparently suitable habitat. Indeed, our data suggest that the territories of paired and unpaired males were generally comparable in terms of vegetation structure and predation risk. While numerous studies have linked mobility to being a “non-breeder,” this is generally done within the context of the dichotomous “territorial vs. floater” framework rather than a mate-searching framework (Smith and Arcese 1989; Winker 1998; Penteriani et al. 2011). In the former, movement by floaters is viewed as an involuntary consequence of being unable to occupy a territory in suitable habitat and is expected to cease once such a territory has been attained. Thus, a males’s unpaired status *per se* is not viewed as the cause of his mobility, but rather both his breeding status and spatial behavior are considered to be the result of exclusion from suitable habitat. We are aware of four territorial songbird species for which there are published studies suggesting or at least

considering that dispersive movements by unpaired males could be related to mate searching (Ortulan Bunting *Emberiza hortulana*, Dale et al. 2005; Dale and Steifetten 2011; Scarlet Tanagers *Piranga olivacea*, Fraser and Stutchbury 2004; Common Nightingale *Luscinia megarhynchos*, Amrhein et al. 2007; Kirtland's Warbler *Setophaga kirtlandii*, Cooper and Marra 2020).

In support of our second prediction, we found that paired males occupying a territory with low current mating potential (i.e., with a female that was laying or incubating eggs) were more likely to move to a secondary territory (i.e., become polyterritorial) than paired males occupying a territory where the current mating potential was high. This temporal pattern in male propensity to move to a secondary territory has previously been documented in studies of polyterritoriality in Wood Warblers (Temrin and Jakobsson 1988) as well as other species (Alatalo and Lundberg 1984; Secunda and Sherry 1991). It also parallels the temporal patterns observed in male extra-territorial forays (Evans et al. 2008; Churchill and Hannon 2010; Akçay et al. 2012) and extra-pair mating behavior (Canal et al. 2012; García-Navas et al. 2015; Kaiser et al. 2017), highlighting that temporary emigration by males appears to be frequent during the period between the decline in their mate's copulatory activity and the onset of paternal care. Despite these similarities between male polyterritorial and foraging behavior, it appears they have not previously been explicitly linked as manifestations of the same phenomenon, namely mate searching.

Our final analysis showed that whether a male dispersed following a nest predation event was contingent on whether the female remained to reneest, consistent with our third prediction. Males never abandoned a territory following nest predation if the female remained to reneest

(n=6), while they had a high probability of doing so if she dispersed or died (n=23). While our sample sizes are small, these results strongly suggest that the cue for male emigration following nest failure is the loss of the female rather than the perceived risk of nest predation itself. A similar suggestion was made by Davies (1992) following the observation that male dunnocks (*Prunella modularis*) almost invariably abandoned their territory following predation if it no longer provided access to a female, but remained if it did. While we are unaware of any study confirming male emigration following nest predation in the absence of female emigration, reports of females leaving independently are widespread (Jackson et al. 1989; Hoover 2003; García-Navas and Sanz 2011). Thus, it seems that female departure modulates male decisions to move in response to nest predation, and observations of pairs dispersing together may be the result of males following females to a new nesting location (Gow and Stutchbury 2013; Lang et al. 2002; Greig-Smith 1982). We suspect that most pairs in our study did not remain together when moving to a new territory after nest predation, since in three of the four cases of female dispersal (≥ 150 m) for which we found the reneest, females paired with a new male. Given that the furthest distance between female nesting locations that we documented was 6.25 km, many of the females who disappeared may have moved several km or more to reneest.

Taken together, our results indicate that the decisions of male Wood Warblers to move to another territory, either temporarily or permanently, are modulated by female availability. We suggest there are two demographic reasons why our data fit especially well within the mate searching framework, which merit further discussion. The first is that Wood Warbler densities in our study region are low relative to other regions (maximum 4 males/10 ha, 3 females/10 ha compared to > 20 pairs/10 ha in eastern Europe, (Cramp 1992). Moving to another territory is

only a viable option if alternative territories are available, such that both dispersal (Serrano and Tella 2003; Carro et al. 2016) and polyterritoriality (Secunda and Sherry 1991; Zając et al. 2008) are often expressed facultatively at low population densities. The second is that the adult sex ratio in our study population is male-biased (males outnumber females by ca. 2:1). Theoretical (Meier et al. 2011; Shaw and Kokko 2014) as well as empirical studies in diverse taxa (arthropods, Muniz et al. 2018; Mishra et al. 2020; birds, Steifetten and Dale 2012; Kempenaers and Valcu 2017; primates, Olupot and Waser 2001; Jack and Fedigan 2004) show that local rarity of (fertile) females often induces emigration in males. Because adult mortality is generally female-biased in birds (Liker and Székely 2005; Székely et al. 2014), male-biased adult sex ratios are common, and tend to be particularly prevalent in small and declining populations (Donald 2007). Given that bird populations are declining across the globe (Bowler et al. 2019; Şekercioğlu et al. 2019; Rosenberg et al. 2019), the socioecological conditions favoring mobile behavior in males are likely widespread and increasing.

The above discussion of population density, sex ratio and movement has a bearing on Greenwood's hypothesis and the "territorial vs. floater" framework within which it is embedded. What Greenwood (1980) attributed to the benefit of familiarity in a resource defense mating system, may instead represent optimal behavior in a particular set of socioecological circumstances – namely, a high population density and balanced sex ratio. In such situations, occupying a territory (particularly in high quality habitat) will quite likely lead to access to a female. Furthermore, if local habitats are saturated, movement to occupy a different territory (either temporarily or permanently) will probably require fighting. Thus, males may remain in a single territory not because familiarity is intrinsically beneficial, but because the costs of trying

to evict other males are too great. It is likely in these situations that males then resort to “covert” forays to gain access to females by means that do not involve defense of a new territory.

We emphasize that we are not the first to highlight limitations of Greenwood’s hypothesis, particularly that it is based on a tenuous dichotomization of “resource-defense” vs. “female defense” mating systems (Ostfeld 1987; Clarke et al. 1997; Trochet et al. 2016). Furthermore, evidence for a relationship between male territoriality and female-biased dispersal in birds has been equivocal in recent reviews (Clarke et al. 1997; Trochet et al. 2016). Nevertheless, the notion that male resource defense (i.e., territoriality) promotes male philopatry is still prevalent (Serrano et al. 2021; Trochet et al. 2016). As noted above, implicit in this hypothesis is the assumption that occupying a territory in good habitat will lead to access to a mate, which renders further movement unnecessary. While the four decades since Greenwood proposed his hypothesis have revealed male within-season movements to be widespread (Whitaker and Warkentin 2010; Williams and Boyle 2018; Cooper and Marra 2020; Ceresa et al. 2020), explanations for this behavior remain consistent with the assumption that a territory in good habitat should not be left (i.e., movement is a response to ecological conditions). In other words, we seem to readily ascribe male emigration decisions to suboptimal habitat because, according to conventional wisdom, a male gains access to mates by securing a good territory and then waiting for females to settle within it. Although the literature on polyterritoriality demonstrates that male songbirds shift their locus of territorial activity in response to a perceived reduction in mating potential in their current territory, this evidence has had limited influence on the avian dispersal literature. We therefore reiterate previous calls for more integration and cross-talk between the topics of mate searching and dispersal (Meier et al. 2011; Gilroy and Lockwood

2012; Shaw and Kokko 2014; Li and Kokko 2019), and between “movement types” more generally (Shaw, 2020). The framework presented here is intended as a step in this direction.

We conclude by highlighting that more explicit recognition of mate searching as a driver of movement in male birds is not only a matter of academic relevance, but may also be important for conservation efforts. As an example, multiple recent studies have related within-season changes in site occupancy to various habitat features, and have interpreted such “apparent movement” as an adaptation allowing individuals (of both sexes) to track heterogeneity or fluctuations in ecological resources (Betts et al. 2008; Gilroy et al. 2010; McClure and Hill 2012; Frey et al. 2016; Ceresa et al. 2020). These studies are based on data from censusing techniques in which it is primarily vocalizing individuals (and therefore, often males) that are detected and counted, and access to mates is neither quantified nor considered as a potential explanation for movement. While it is well possible that the observed changes in the distribution of males is due to resource tracking by breeding pairs, assuming this is the case could result in a failure to recognize a larger demographic problem – namely, a lack of females. Rather than being an intrinsic feature of species inhabiting dynamic environments, a high frequency of within-season movements may instead be a symptom of failure to find a mate. From a conservation perspective, distinguishing between ecological resource tracking and mate searching is important because the latter could reflect a problem that habitat modifications alone may fail to address.

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Statement of Authorship

Conceptualization: S.B.L. and G.P.; Funding acquisition: G.P.; Data collection: S.B.L. and Z.Z.; Data analysis: S.B.L. and F.K.-N.; Supervision: G.P.; Writing – original draft: S.B.L.; Writing – review & editing: S.B.L., F.K.-N., G.P.

Data and Code Accessibility

Data and codes are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8382146> (Luepold et al. 2023).

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Tables

Table 1. Standardized estimates with 95% credible intervals (CrI) from two sets of logistic regression models used to assess whether habitat conditions in a territory predict the dispersal decisions of Wood Warbler males. Set 1 relates probability of territory occupation by a paired male to habitat parameters, Set 2 relates probability of being the second (i.e., moved to) territory to habitat parameters.

Parameter ^c	Set 1: probability of occupation by paired male ^a		Set 2: probability of being second territory occupied ^b	
	Standard deviation	Standardized estimate (95% CrI)	Standard deviation	Standardized estimate (95% CrI)
meanVH	3.10	-0.04 (-0.42 – 0.36)	3.49	-0.38 (-0.93 – 0.15)
sdCH3	1.42	-0.14 (-0.55 – 0.25)	1.35	0.33 (-0.20 – 0.88)
pen5_1	0.14	-0.10 (-0.49 – 0.30)	0.15	0.12 (-0.40 – 0.64)
RAI	56.69	0.23 (-0.40 – 0.96)	57.80	-0.17 (-1.16 – 0.87)

^a Model with LiDAR variables (meanVH, sdCH3 and pen5_1), included 54 territories of unpaired males and 61 territories of paired males; model with RAI included 25 territories of unpaired males and 16 territories of paired males.

^b Model with LiDAR variables (meanVH, sdCH3 and pen5_1), included first and second territories of 33 males; model with RAI included first and second territories of 10 males.

° meanVH = mean vegetation height; sdCH3 = standard deviation of canopy height > 3m; pen5_1 = penetration rate 5 to 1 m above ground; RAI = rodent activity index (proxy of predation risk). See main text and supporting information S2 for more detailed description of habitat metrics.

Table 2. Estimated effects with 95% credible intervals (CrI) for parameters in the model of polyterritorial movement probability of male Wood Warblers (n=95 observations, 62 males).

Parameter*	Estimate (95% CrI)
Mate Low	2.97 (0.94 – 5.87)
Local Density	-0.75 (-2.03 – 0.31)
Intercept	-3.97 (-7.04 – -1.93)
sd(ID)	0.87 (0.03 – 2.58)

**Mate Low*: low mating potential in the current territory (factor *Mate* has two levels, *Mate High* is reference level); *Local Density*: number of conspecifics within 150 m radius of focal male; *sd(ID)*: standard deviation of male ID (random effect).

Table 3. Estimated effects with 95% credible intervals (CrI) for parameters in model of dispersal probability of male Wood Warblers following nest predation (n=29).

Parameter*	Estimate (95% CrI)
Mate Zero	19.38 (4.11 – 55.54)
Local Density	1.68 (-0.99 – 5.22)
Intercept	-18.12 (-54.16 – -2.90)

**Mate Zero*: zero mating potential in the current territory (factor *Mate* has two levels, *Mate High* is reference level); *Local Density*: number of conspecifics within 150 m radius of focal male.

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1. Predicted within-season movement decisions of male birds according to the mate searching framework. Even when habitat in the current territory is apparently suitable, males will still choose to leave in response to perceived low mating potential (e.g, if a female fails to arrive or, in the case of polyterritoriality, is no longer in her fertile peak); when ecological conditions in the current territory are apparently poor, males will nevertheless choose to stay if a female is (remains) available. Thus, perceived low mating potential in the current territory is consistently the primary modulator of male movement decisions, regardless of apparent ecological conditions.

Figure 2. Comparison of Wood Warbler territories occupied by unpaired males and paired males in four habitat features. Panels A–C show three LiDAR-derived metrics representing vegetation structure (meanVH = mean vegetation height; sdCH3 = standard deviation of canopy height > 3m; pen5_1 = penetration rate 5 to 1 m above ground). Panel D shows a proxy of predation risk (RAI = rodent activity index).

Figure 3. Comparison of habitat features in the first and second known territories of individual unpaired Wood Warbler males. Panels A–C show three LiDAR-derived metrics representing vegetation structure in successive territories of 33 males (meanVH = mean vegetation height; sdCH3 = standard deviation of canopy height > 3m; pen5_1 = penetration rate 5 to 1 m above ground). Panel D shows a proxy of predation risk (RAI = rodent activity index) in the successive territories of 10 males.

Figure 4. Probability of male polyterritorial movement (A) and male dispersal after nest predation (B) in relation to mating potential in the current territory. Error bars show 95% credible intervals. Numbers in parentheses indicate number of unique individuals in each mating potential category.

Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 3

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Figure 4

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Supplemental Material

It's about her: male within-season movements are related to mate searching in a songbird

The American Naturalist

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S1. Movement detection for birds with and without transmitters

To address the concern that we may have detected movements of longer distances when birds were fitted with transmitters, we compared distances moved by birds with and without transmitters. Out of 36 movements made by 25 birds with transmitters, the median distance was 559 m (range: 165 – 2186 m). Out of 28 movements made by 20 birds without transmitters, the mean distance was 627 m (range: 150 – 4156 m). Therefore, observed movement distances were not longer in birds with transmitters, and we pooled data from birds with and without transmitters.

S2. Description and derivation of variables representing habitat features

Rodent activity index (RAI)

We used track plates to assess local rodent activity (Grendelmeier et al. 2017; Connors et al. 2005). While this method does not provide precise estimations of local abundance, it has been found to be a reliable index of small mammal activity that correlates with predation probability of their prey (Connors et al. 2005). In 2017, we assessed rodents in two sites, encompassing a total area of ca. 110 ha. We assessed three sites in 2018, covering an area of ca. 130 ha.

We determined plate locations by overlaying each study site with 5-ha circular plots (corresponding to a radius of 125 m), within which we delineated a 50x50 m grid. We placed plates at each of the resulting 21 nodes within each 5-ha plot. Plates were constructed from 3-mm thick sheets of white PVC, cut into 25x30 cm rectangles. In the field, we applied a liquid mixture of graphite, ethanol and paraffin oil to the plates and left them for 48 hours. We then photographed each plate (with a tablet or smart phone) for subsequent analysis (Fig. S1A). To facilitate counting, we divided each plate photograph into quadrants and counted tracks for 30 seconds within each quadrant. To increase consistency between plates, we restricted our counts to “scratch marks,” which were linear features clearly identifiable as tracks and

distinguishable from pock marks caused by dripping vegetation or the spray application of the graphite mixture.

Based on the plate counts and locations for each site/year, we created a continuous 10x10 m raster surface of rodent activity using inverse distance weighted interpolation (Fig. S1B) in the R package *gstat* (Pebesma 2004; Gräler et al. 2016). We used the simple kriging formula (counts ~ 1) and the default settings of the *idw* function (inverse distance weighting power was 2).

Figure S1. Example of track plate with linear “scratch marks” (A); raster based on inverse distance weighted interpolation of track plate counts in 2017 and 2018 (B). Hollow circles indicate locations of 25-m radius territories.

LiDAR Data

Laser scanning flights were made in April 2018, yielding classified point clouds representing a digital terrain model (DTM) and a digital surface model (DSM). The mean number of points per 25 m radius territory was 157,564 (range: 48,064 – 442,503).

Interpolation of the DTM across a 2x2 m grid was used to create the digital elevation model

“swissALTI3D” (<https://www.swisstopo.admin.ch/en/geodata/height/alti3d.html>). A normalised digital surface model (nDSM) was calculated by subtracting the DSM from the swissALTI3D. Vegetation height (VH) corresponds to the normalised digital surface model (nDSM). The variable we used in our analysis was the mean VH within a 25 m radius circle centered on each territory point (*meanVH*). Canopy height above 3 m (CH>3) corresponds to the maximum LiDAR signal for each cell in a 1x1 m grid, based on laser signals reflecting from objects more than 3 m above ground. In our analysis, we used the standard deviation of CH>3 values (*sdCH3*) within a 25 m radius circle centered on each territory point. This variable thus reflects heterogeneity of canopy height. The penetration variable *pen5_1* represents the ratio of the sum of all LiDAR signals below 1 m above ground to the sum of all LiDAR signals below 5 m above ground, and reflects the structure of the herbaceous and shrub layers. A high penetration corresponds to sparse vegetation. As with the previous two variables, penetration values were summed across each 25 m radius circular territory.

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